

Research

Numerical investigation of performance evaluation of Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROV) using CFD approach

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Abstract: Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) is mainly used for many tasks and applications, such as exploration of the sea. The designing and optimization of ROV systems have great potential to enhance performance and working mechanisms. In this research work, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analyses of five different ROV underwater vehicles were performed for the model modification. In addition, CFD analysis of the best suitable thruster model was also conducted in order to examine the flow behavior around the thruster body. Moreover, the performance of ROV systems and thruster were also conducted in order to select an optimized ROV model. For this purpose, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analyses of five different ROV models and one modified thruster model were performed using ANSYS FLUENT. CFD analyses were performed at different water flow velocities such as 1 m/s, 1.5 m/s, 2 m/s, 2.5 m/s, 3 m/s and 3.5 m/s for the depth range of 4m to 50m. The drag force, pressure contours, and velocity contours were computed at different water flow velocities to examine and select the modified ROV model with the lowest drag force. According to computed results, the maximum drag forces are observed for model 4, and the minimum drag forces are observed for model 5. The larger computed drag force values are due to the maximum contact area of water flowing around the ROV model. In model 5 of the ROV model, the flow of water impacted minimum on the frontal area and observed the lowest value of drag force. The maximum and minimum values of the drag forces for model 5 are 6.40062 N and 0.60606 N at water flow velocities of 3.5 m/s and 1m/s, respectively. On the other hand, it can be observed from the computed results of the thruster model that the maximum hydraulic pressure was obtained at a water flow velocity of 3.5 m/s, and the minimum value was observed at 1m/s. Finally, it was concluded from the obtained results that ROV model 5 is the best suitable model for underwater application at a depth range of 4m to 50m. The results obtained from this study can be very helpful for engineers and researchers in order to model and optimize ROV models using a numerical approach.

Keywords: ROV; Drag Force; CFD Fluent; Thruster; SST k-w

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Introduction

The requirement for seabed surveys prompted the development of modern underwater technology. New methodologies have been developed since the 1950s, but even in the 1960s, when the offshore gas fields in the southern North Sea were established, knowledge of seabed stratigraphy was limited [1]. All potential fixed platform sites must be surveyed with sufficient precision to ensure a flat, even seabed, for stability and carry the concentrated load for subsea structure foundation. In more than one instance in the North Sea, operators have been faced with a last-minute change of site or a hurried clearance of boulders from a site because of insufficient information from initial surveys. These circumstances highlight the need for more detailed underwater surveys and improved underwater positioning and navigation tools. Once a viable line has been chosen, a geophysical study of the underlying strata is done to determine the suitability of the seabed sediment for burying the pipeline. After completion, annual side-scan sonar and sub-bottom profile surveys are required to verify the burial depth. Following a series of failures beginning in the 1970s, offshore oil companies realized the importance of conducting underwater surveys of the seafloor and sub-seabed conditions before beginning any offshore engineering work, such as platform installation, pipeline laying, or semisubmersible anchoring. In general, such a survey's cost is insignificant compared to the potential hazard and expense of a seafloor collapse. As exploration has progressed deeper into the ocean, Under the Offshore Installations Regulations of 1975, a diving bell must be used below 50 meters. Saturation diving has become important as decompression times have increased [2]. To overcome the obstacles of decompression, the offshore industry has developed a variety of atmospheric diving suits, manned and unmanned submersibles, and underwater surveying and inspection activities. Driverless techniques have become the favored solution in deep water. Many underwater jobs necessitate using an ROV (Remote Operated Vehicle) as a primary or backup working system. The general purpose ROV is equipped with various data collecting equipment and modern manipulators for manipulating objects. Specially built underwater tooling systems have been developed, such as high precision maintenance equipment, devices with repair capability and override function, and equipment with great lifting or pulling capacity. Many of the pieces of equipment, such as pipeline tie-ins and platform tension leg tightening, were pre-designed for installation operations [3]. One approach to considering the evolution of ROVs is to consider them in terms of the life cycle - from infancy to maturity. Anyone who has ever raised a child can attest to this. Comprehend a classification like this. The ROV kid was initially a problem: their bottles spilled, their hydraulics failed, they were harmed by sunshine, they were excessively noisy and unreliable, they were difficult to manage, and they required frequent maintenance [4]. In 1953 The Poodle was the first ROV ever built, developed by Dimitri Rebikoff, a French pioneer in diving equipment and photography? The Poodle was an unmanned version of his diving scooter, with cable and surface controls. The US Navy began employing ROV for underwater equipment retrieval in the 1960s and has since advanced the technology. By the 1980s, the world had more than 500 ROVs, many of which were employed for commercial purposes. ROVs have grown in popularity in a wide range of sectors since then, with tens of thousands of ROVs worldwide [5]. In 1966, the CURV rescued a lost atomic weapon from 2850 feet (869 meters) of the sea off the coast of Palomares, Spain, despite operating beyond its maximum depth. In 1973, CURV III, which had evolved into a 'flyaway' system, was dispatched on an emergency rescue mission from San Diego to a location off the coast of Cork, Ireland. The CURV III connected a rescue line that successfully hauled the doomed crew to safety with little air left for the two pilots of the PISCES III manned submersible, which was stuck on the bottom in 1575 feet (480 meters) of water [6]. Despite being effective in their design aims, these new invaders were unable to break the market lock held by human submersibles and saturation divers. These underwater robots are frequently controlled by a human on a surface vessel using a joystick, similar to how a video game is operated. Abdollah Sakaki et al. [7] determined an underwater vehicle's hydrodynamic forces and coefficient using a numerical and experimental approach. They used Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) FLUENT to measure the hydrodynamic coefficient and flow characteristics over the vehicle body for numerical analysis. Andra Teodora NEDELICU et al. [8] conducted a CFD analysis of ROV in

the horizontal plane to examine the flow behavior around the ROV body and found the pressure and velocity distribution. They modeled the ROV vehicle body with the Six-Degree-of-Freedom equation to reflect its hydrodynamics behavior. Luca Pugi et al. [9] introduced a reconfigurable propulsion layout and carried out performance with a conventional one. They also focused on the modeling approach and its techniques, which represented an acceptable trade-off in terms of accuracy and involved computational resources for fast prototyping and simulation of this type of mechanical system. Ingrid Schjølberg et al. [10] presented an innovation, and future aspects mainly focused on the development of the technology to enable autonomy in ROV operations. Thant Zin Htun et al. [11] proposed accurate ROV tether cable system modeling with radially multilayered circular cross-sections. Romi Wiryadinata et al. [12] designed a prototype ROV model and tested it with 3 DOF controlled by a joystick connected with UTP cables which can be used as data controlled between the joystick with a microcontroller embedded in the robot. Thanh-Long Le et al. [13] performed a CFD analysis to develop a physical model representing all important features of the autonomous underwater vehicles' body shape using the Finite Element Method. Javier Neira et al. [14] presented a comprehensive review of the ROV research to make an effort a walkthrough of evolution in order to show a diversity of structure designs, the material used in ROV model, sensors and instruments approaches and a different number of actuators employed, navigation control techniques and what is the new development trends, etc. Ying He et al. [15] presented comprehensive reviews on ROV research to describe the innovation of ROV models; their different kinds mainly focused on control systems. They also offered a brief introduction to unmanned underwater vehicles together with ROUV systems. Guan Zhiguang et al. [16] developed underwater vehicle equipment and described a control system in detail based on the self-developed ROV vehicles. They also conducted an experimental analysis and showed that the control system of the self-development ROV vehicle could satisfy the usage requirement. According to current literature, it was investigated that Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) can be utilized to evaluate the performance of ROV models. It was also examined from the current literature, many of the authors had researched on modification of ROV model of the one model based on different parameters such as drag force and other geometrical parameters, but there has not been yet studied the CFD analysis of five different ROV models to modify the lowest drag force ROV model for sea exploration applications. In this current research work, using a numerical approach, five different ROV models were performed to find the lowest drag force ROV model. Performance analysis of the modified thruster model was also carried out to apply the modified ROV model. In this research, the main purpose is to examine the five different ROV models and find the best suitable ROV model for drag reduction applications. For this purpose, CFD analyzes five different ROV models to find the lowest drag force, model. The commercial software ANSYS FLUENT 19.0 was used. The CFD analyses of five different ROV models were performed at different flow velocities such as 1 m/s, 1.5 m/s, 2 m/s, 2.5 m/s, 3 m/s and 3.5 m/s. The drag forces and drag coefficient of all ROV models were performed. Moreover, CFD analysis of best suitable thruster model was also conducted at different water flow velocities.

Numerical Methodology

Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) analyses of five different ROV models were performed at various water flowing velocities (1 m/s, 1.5 m/s, 2 m/s, 2.5 m/s, 3 m/s, 3.5 m/s) to determine the drag force and drag coefficient of the ROV models. In addition, the pressure distribution, velocity distribution, and flow streamlines were also examined from CFD post-processing. Similarly, CFD analysis of the thruster was also conducted to examine the flow characteristics around the thruster rotor blades. The complete description of the numerical methodology of ROV models is shown in Figure 1.

Flow Simulation of ROV Model

Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis of five different ROV models and thrusters was performed at different water flow velocities. CFD tool is mostly used to calculate the flow characteristics and to determine the drag force on the ROV body and thruster rotor blade surfaces. The computational fluid dynamic (CFD) simulation of ROV models and thruster model is performed to obtain hydraulic load and velocity distribution on the ROV model surfaces and thruster blade surfaces, the short description of CFD modeling is described in the following sections.

Physical Model

The first step in CFD modeling is to create a physical 3D CAD model of the fluid domain for fluid flow simulation according to a given condition [17]. The physical 3D model is made in Solidworks, and the Solidworks file is imported into CFD fluid fluent. The computation domain is generated in the ANSYS fluent design modeler, and the ROV model lies inside the computation domain. The computation domain is completely constructed by deducting the ROV model from the fluid domain. Five different ROV models and thruster model are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Methodology flow chart of CFD analysis of different ROV models

Figure 2: 3D-CAD models of five different ROV models and thruster model; (a) ROV model 1 (b) ROV model 2 (c) ROV model 3 (d) ROV model 4 (e) ROV model 5 (f) Thruster model

Computational Domain

The computational domain also plays a crucial role in CFD simulations. The computational domain is the streamlined form of physical discipline or area in which various governing equations, such as the equation of continuity, energy conservation, and equation of momentum, are calculated [18]. For example, when we create the ROV's computational domain to investigate the ROV model's aerodynamic behavior, we create a rectangular box in which the solid body of the ROV model is subtracted. A complete description of the computational domain of the ROV model is given in three-dimensional views shown in Figure 3. In addition, 2D drawings of ROV models with dimensions are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Description of the three-dimensional computational domain

Figure 4: 2D-CAD drawings of five different ROV models and thruster model; (a) ROV model 1 (b) ROV model 2 (c) ROV model 3 (d) ROV model 4 (e) ROV model 5

Grid generation in ANSYS Mechanical

After creating the computational domain in ANSYS fluent 19.0, it is important to generate a better quality mesh for appropriate results [19]. In this study, tetrahedron, the unstructured mesh, is created, having 713111 nodes and 4080993 elements. Mesh of three-dimensional flow domain or computational domain and cut section of mesh structure are shown in Figure 5. A very fine mesh is drawn on the surfaces of the ROV model for the accuracy of the results.

Figure 5: Mesh of the three-dimensional flow domain

Mathematical modeling of numerical simulation

The flowing fluid field near the turbine region in the stream can be described using the Reynolds number. The Reynolds number can be expressed below [20]

$$Re = \frac{\rho U_{\infty} D}{\mu} \tag{1}$$

Where Re is Reynolds number, ρ is the fluid density, U_{∞} is the free stream velocity, D is the diameter, μ and is the dynamic viscosity. The numerical simulations were performed for a Reynolds number $\sim 14.33 \times 10^6$ which is based on the outer diameter of the computational domain, and $\sim 1.02 \times 10^6$ which is based on the tip diameter of the turbine runner [12]. The K- ω SST, the most useful turbulence model, is adopted for numerical simulation that solves two different transport equations for defining turbulent kinetic energy and dissipation rate. The governing equations for the turbine are used to perform numerical simulations that are considered under the following expectations: it has a three-dimensional incompressible and steady-state flow. Based on these expectations following equations can be written as: [19]

Equation of conservation of mass

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \tag{2}$$

Equation of conservation of momentum

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} \right) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + S_M \tag{3}$$

Where \mathbf{u} is the velocity vector, ρ is density, t is time, p is the pressure, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the stress tensor, S_M is the momentum source.

Equation of turbulence kinetic energy

$$\frac{\partial k}{\partial t} + U_j \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} = \tau_{ij} \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} - \beta^* k \omega + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[(\nu + \sigma_k \nu_T) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] \tag{4}$$

Equation of specific dissipation rate

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} + U_j \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} = \alpha S^2 - \beta \omega^2 + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[(\nu + \sigma_\omega \nu_T) \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \right] + 2(1 - F_1) \sigma_{\omega 2} \frac{1}{\omega} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \quad (5)$$

Where k turbulence kinetic energy ω is the specific dissipation rate, α the closure coefficient, and the mean rate-of-strain tensor F_1 is the blending function.

Results and Discussion

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analyses of five different ROV model are performed to determine the drag force and examine the flow characteristics around the ROV walls. In addition, CFD analyses of the thruster model are also performed at different water flow velocities. The water flow velocities of 1 m/s, 1.5 m/s, 2 m/s, 2.5 m/s, 3 m/s and 3.5 m/s for ROV models and thruster are used for CFD analyses. Variations of drag force with the variation of water flow velocities for five different ROV models are represented in Figure 6. Moreover, the computed results are also listed in Table 1. It can be seen from the computed results in table 1 that drag forces are increased with the increase of flow velocity. According to computed results, the maximum drag forces are observed for model 4, and minimum drag forces are observed for model 5. The larger computed values of drag forces are due to the maximum contact area of water flowing around the ROV model. In model 5 of the ROV model, the flowing water impacted minimum on the frontal area and observed the lowest value of drag force. The maximum and minimum values of the drag forces for model 5 are 6.40062 N and 0.60606 N at water flow velocities of 3.5 m/s and 1m/s, respectively.

Table 1: Computed values of drag forces for five different ROV models

Flow Velocity (m/s)	Drag Force for Model 1 (N)	Drag Force for Model 2 (N)	Drag Force for Model 3 (N)	Drag Force for Model 4 (N)	Drag Force for Model 5 (N)
1	19.6683	4.30456	12.7832	129.645	0.60606
1.5	43.63	9.27632	28.8375	290.005	1.28549
2	79.4556	16.4015	51.1488	513.807	2.20683
2.5	119.283	24.9489	80.2908	800.582	3.37298
3	171.134	35.5734	115.361	1150.8	4.77394
3.5	232.168	47.9121	156.405	1564.3	6.40062

Furthermore, the flow characteristics for other different models were also examined. The graphical representations of variation of drag forces with different water flow velocities are shown in Figure 6. It can be seen from the figure that maximum drag forces were observed for ROV model 4, and minimum drag forces were observed for ROV model 5. The maximum exposed area of the ROV model causes maximum drag force. It can also be observed that the maximum exposed area to water flow was in ROV model 4. Thus, the maximum pressure was also monitored in ROV model 4 at the frontal area.

Similarly, the minimum exposed area was examined in ROV model 5. Thus the minimum drag force was observed in ROV model 5. The pressure and velocity distribution for five different ROV models are represented in Figures 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16. Similarly, the pressure distribution and velocity distribution of the thruster were also represented in Figure 17. The pressure and velocity distributions can observe the vortexes generated at the back end of ROV models. On the other hand, the maximum pressure drop occurred in ROV model 5.

Figure 6: Variation of drag forces with the variation of flow velocities for three different ROV models

Figure 7: Variation of drag forces with the variation of flow velocities for model 1

Figure 8: Variation of drag forces with the variation of flow velocities for model 2

Figure 9: Variation of drag forces with the variation of flow velocities for model 3

Figure 10: Variation of drag forces with the variation of flow velocities for model 4

The maximum pressure drop was due to a larger area where water flow generates vortices. Furthermore, CFD analysis of the thruster model was also carried out to determine the maximum pressure on the blade surfaces and evaluate the performance of the thruster model. The analyses were conducted at different water flow velocities. It was also examined from Figure 12 that maximum pressure was observed at a flow velocity of 3.5 m/s, and minimum pressure was examined at 1 m/s. The increment of pressure distribution is due to the increment of water flow velocities.

Figure 11: Variation of drag forces with the variation of flow velocities for model 5

Flow simulations of five different ROV models and one thruster model are presented in Figure 12 to 16 and 17 respectively. Figure 12 describes the pressure and velocity contours of model 1. It can be seen from the obtained results that maximum pressure exerted on the frontal area of the ROV model may cause higher drag force in model 1. In addition, vortices were also generated on the back side of the ROV model, which may decrease the thruster's performance. Figure 13 shows the pressure and velocity contours of ROV model 2. The drag force generated in model 2 is less than that generated in model 1. Thus, ROV model 2 is better in terms of lower drag force than ROV model. There has been less pressure exerted on the frontal area of the ROV model 2. In addition, vortices generated due to flowing water were also observed lower compared to model 1. Furthermore, figure 15 represents the thruster model flow characteristics such as pressure contours and velocity contours. It can be seen from the obtained results that maximum pressure is generated on the frontal area of the blades of the thruster model. It can be observed from the obtained results that maximum pressure is generated at flow velocities of 3.5 m/s, and the minimum pressure is generated at flow velocities of 1 m/s. In addition, the thruster's performance is also within an acceptable range and can perform well. The selected thruster model is the optimized model used in the optimized ROV model.

Figure 12: Pressure distribution and velocity distribution for ROV model 1 at different flow velocities

Figure 13 Pressure distribution and velocity distribution for ROV model 2 at different flow velocities

Figure 14: Pressure distribution and velocity distribution for ROV model 3 at different flow velocities

Figure 15: Pressure distribution and velocity distribution for ROV model 4 at different flow velocities

Figure 16: Pressure distribution and velocity distribution for ROV model 5 at different flow velocities

Figure 17: Pressure distribution and velocity distribution for ROV thruster at different flow velocities

In addition, pressure distribution and velocity distribution of ROV models 5 is also shown in Figure 16. It can be seen from Figure 16 that maximum pressure is generated at the frontal beam of the ROV structure by flowing the water over the model. The maximum and minimum pressure values are observed at a flow velocity of 3.5 m/s and 1m/s,

respectively. Similarly, flow characteristics of ROV model 5 were also examined to follow the flow regime over the ROV wall. Pressure and velocity distributions are shown in Figure 16. ROV model 5 has a narrow frontal shape to reduce the drag force in the model. It can be seen from Figure 16 that maximum pressure is exerted at the frontal limited shape area and minimum at the tail of the ROV model. It has also been studied that less drag force is examined in ROV model 5. Therefore, ROV model 5 is the lowest drag force model. The reason behind this reduced drag force is due to the narrow shape of the front and back sides of the ROV model. Therefore, this model also has a certain depth range. Flow characteristics of ROV model 5 are shown in Figure 16.

The performance of ROV vehicles can be evaluated using a variety of factors. In one of them, depth is an important parameter that impacts significantly on the performance of ROV. In this study, the impact of depth on the performance of ROV was evaluated at different flow velocities. For this purpose, CFD analyses of ROV bodies were conducted for different depth and flow velocities of 3.5 m/s. The depth of ROV bodies for performance evaluation was chosen 10m, 20m, and 30m. Similarly, the flow velocity of 3.5 m/s was kept.

Figure 18: Comparison of drag forces and water flow velocities at different depth

The graphical representations of variation of drag force with different flow velocities at different water depths are shown in Figures 18 to 21. Figure 18 represents the comparison graph of drag force and water velocity at different depths of 10 m, 20 m, and 30 m. It is evident from figure 21 that the maximum drag force was observed for a water depth of 10 m. Similarly, the minimum drag force was examined for a depth of 30 m. This decrement in drag force is due to the increase of water impact beneath the water. The water flow velocity on the surface of the water is larger than beneath the water. Thus, the effect of hydraulic load at 10 m of the water is higher than beneath the water. Moreover, the individual graphical representations of variation of drag force at different water flow velocities at water depth of 10m, 20m and 30m are also presented in Figure 19, 20 and 21.

Figure 19: Variation of drag force with water velocity at a water depth of 10 m

Figure 19 shows the variation of drag force with water flow velocities at a water depth of 10 m. It is evident from the computed results that the maximum and minimum values of drag forces of 235.25 N and 21.23 N were recorded for water velocities of 3.5 m/s and 1 m/s at a depth of 10 m, respectively. The graphical trend is linearly increased with the increase of water flow velocities. Furthermore, it can be observed that the impact of water increased with the increase in water depth. The variation of drag force with water flow velocities at water depths of 20 m and 30 m are also represented in Figures 20 and 21. Figure 20 shows the graphical representation of drag force and water flow velocities at a water depth of 20 m.

Figure 20: Variation of drag force with water velocity at a water depth of 20 m

The maximum and minimum values of drag forces of 158.24 N and 13.85 N were examined at velocities of 3.5 m/s and 1 m/s at a depth of 20 m, respectively. It can also be seen from the computed results that the drag force is lower as compared to the depth of 10 m. Similarly, graphical representations of drag force and water velocity for a depth of 30 m are also shown in Figure 21. In the same way, the maximum and minimum values of drag forces of 49.58 N and 5.47 N were observed at different flow velocities for the depth of 30 m. The main reason behind this decrement with the increasing depth of water is lower hydraulic impact force on the ROV bodies. Thus, fewer values of drag forces are recorded at a depth of 30 m.

Figure 21: Variation of drag force with water velocity at a water depth of 30 m

Conclusion

Computational Fluid Dynamics analyses of five different Remotely Operated Vehicles for the model modification were conducted to select the best suitable and modified ROV vehicle in terms of reduced drag force. In addition, CFD analysis of one thruster model was also examined in order to investigate the flow characteristics such as pressure distribution, velocity distribution, streamlines, etc. For this purpose, CFD analyses were performed at different water flow velocities at a depth range of 4m to 50m. Furthermore, a performance analysis of five different ROV models at different water flow velocities was performed in order to find the lowest drag force ROV model. Additionally, a performance analysis of one thruster model was also performed for the modified ROV model. The CFD analyses were performed at different water flow velocities such as 1 m/s, 1.5 m/s, 2 m/s, 2.5 m/s, 3 m/s, and 3.5 m/s to evaluate the performance and compute the drag force at different water flow velocities.

Furthermore, it can also be observed from the obtained results that drag force increases with the increasing water flow velocities in all ROV models. The maximum drag force value was examined at all ROV models' frontal area. According to results obtained from CFD analyses, the maximum value of drag force was observed for ROV model 4, and the minimum value of drag force was examined for model 5. The main reason behind this larger drag force value is the larger contact area of flowing water around the ROV model. In model 5 of the ROV model, the flow water impact is lower on the frontal area and observed the lowest value of drag force. The maximum and minimum values of the drag forces for model 5 are 6.40062 N and 0.60606 N at water flow velocities of 3.5 m/s and 1 m/s, respectively. Similarly, CFD analysis of one thruster model was also examined to observe the flow behavior around the thruster blades. On the other hand, it can be observed from the computed results of the thruster model that the maximum hydraulic pressure was obtained at a water flow velocity of 3.5 m/s and the minimum value observed at 1 m/s. Finally, it was concluded from the obtained results that ROV model 5 is best suitable model for underwater application at a depth range of 4m to 50m. This research study is useful for engineers and researchers to model and optimize ROV structures for various applications using a numerical approach.

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